

Alignment Guidelines for Greek-Persian

About this Guideline

This annotation style guide is created by Farnoosh Shamsian for the Ugarit Project and is fundamentally based on the Ancient Greek-English guideline created by Chiara Palladino and Farnoosh Shamsian, but it has been modified to address the structural linguistic differences between Ancient Greek and Persian.

General Principles

These guidelines follow the definition of Lambert et al.: “the correspondence between two lexical units (single words or expressions) should involve on both sides as few words as possible, but as many words as necessary, with the requirement that the linked words or groups bear the same meaning [...]. If two single words match, they should be linked together, but if there is no correspondence at a single word level, groups of words should be linked together. Groups of words linked together should be as small as possible.” In addition, “the only valid elements in an alignment are single words and indivisible groups of words” (p.275): groups of words are linked together when the meaning of the group is distinct from that of the sequence of each word’s meaning, and single words cannot be separated from the rest of the group without changing their meaning (= indivisible lexical unit).

Links allowed in Ugarit are one-to-one (1-1), many-to-many (N-N), one-to-many (1-N) and many-to-one (N-1). No distinction can be made between ambiguous and unambiguous, complete or partial links in Ugarit. Words that have no connection are simply left unaligned.

These guidelines can be used to align texts in Ancient Greek and Persian, as well as to build gold standard corpora. They are not, however, project-specific. If you have a particular research question and you need specific results for the purpose of language research, pedagogy, or data mining, you should create your own guidelines (you can reuse any part of these guidelines).

Guidelines

1. Punctuation

Punctuation is never aligned.

2. Words omitted or incorrectly translated

If a group of words only appears in one language whose meaning has no correspondence in the other, it is not aligned.

If a group of words is an incorrect translation of a group of words in the source language, it is not aligned.

3. Phrasal Construction and Idioms

These are expressions that constitute an indivisible lexical unit, where each word singularly does not bear the same meaning, but the group of words together is a semantic equivalent in both languages. They are aligned with a N-N link if there is a Persian equivalent. Examples: dative of possession: 'ἔστιν αὐτοῖς' - 'دارند/ آنان را ... است'; 'ἔτι καὶ νῦν' - 'تاکنون'.

4. Repetition

When a word is repeated in one language but not in the other, only the first instance in each language is aligned.

5. Negation

Whenever possible, negation is aligned with a 1-1 link. However, in most cases that won't be possible, particularly with Persian verb negation which cannot be separated from the verb. In such cases, an N-1 or N-N strategy is recommended. Example: 'ἔστιν οὐ' - 'نیست'.

When the Persian negation morpheme is not attached to the verb, the Greek verb is aligned with the corresponding Persian verb and the negation with the corresponding equivalent, with a 1-1 link wherever possible. Example: in this sentence, each negation should be aligned with the corresponding 'نه' in Persian: οὐ τ' ἄρ' ὁ γ' εὐχλωλῆς ἐπιμέμφεται οὐ δ' ἑκατόμβης - همانا او نه از نیایشی و نه از قربانی شکوه می‌کند

When the structure is changed in Persian, an N-1 or N-N strategy is recommended. Example: 'μή πείθεσθαι' - 'از اطاعت سرپیچی کردن'.

6. Verbs

6.1. Auxiliaries, Verbal Groups

Verbal groups are groups formed by more than one verb: this includes auxiliaries, passivization, translations of tense and aspect, etc.

All verbal groups are aligned as a whole regardless of the number of words. The type of link can be N-N, N-1, or 1-N. Example: 'τελέεσθαι' - 'به انجام خواهد رسید'.

6.2. Verbs and Subjects

Subject of the verb is only aligned when it is explicit in both languages. When the subject is not explicit in both languages, only the verb is aligned. Example: 'ἔσαν' - 'آنان بودند'. ∅- 'آنان', 'ἔσαν' - 'بودند'

These rules also apply to infinitives in infinitive+accusative constructs in Ancient Greek.

6.3. Passive verbs translated into active

Verbs are aligned regardless of voice (active, middle, or passive), provided that the Persian translation bears the same meaning and is correct in the judgment of the annotator. This means that a passive verb in Ancient Greek may be aligned with an active verb in Persian. Example: 'φάανθεν' - 'درخشیدند'.

6.4. Compound verbs with prepositions

Compound verbs (verbs constructed with prepositions in Ancient Greek, e.g. περι-πλέω) are aligned with the corresponding Persian expression, when they are equivalent in meaning.

Example: 'προσηύδα' - 'پیش می خواند'.

In cases of tmesis (a compound verb that appears with preposition separated at the beginning of phrase), the same rule applies, with a N-N link.

Extra prepositions in Persian: when a Persian translation contains an extra preposition that does not explicitly appear in Ancient Greek, the preposition is aligned as part of the verb group, if the Persian requires it in order to make sense. This principle also applies for auxiliaries and similar verb groups. Example: 'διήρηνται' - 'به ... تقسیم شده اند' - 'تقسیم شده اند' in which the preposition به should be included in the alignment together with تقسیم شده اند.

7. Participles in Ancient Greek

7.1. General rules

1. Greek participles translated as a participle, adverb or verb in Persian are aligned as 1-1 or 1-N. The noun that agrees with the participle is aligned separately, with the corresponding translation in Persian. Example: 'ἔχων' - 'گرفته', or 'αὐτοῦ κινήεντος' - 'حرکت کرد' - 'خود' - 'αὐτοῦ': 'خود حرکت کرد'.

2. Participles translated as nouns and adjectives are aligned with the accompanying particle or adposition in Persian that conveys the meaning of the case of the participle. Example: 'Θνήσκοντας ὄρατο': 'مردنشان را می دید': 'Θνήσκοντας' - 'مردنشان را', 'ὄρατο' - 'می دید'
3. Participles translated as a phrase in Persian: the participle is aligned with the whole expression in the Persian translation (1-N). The noun that agrees with the participle is aligned separately, with the corresponding translation in Persian. Example: or 'ἄπαμειβόμενος' - 'در پاسخ'.
4. Substantive and attributive participles: when translated explicitly (mostly as a relative clause), the participle is aligned with the full explicit translation. Example: τοὺς μὲν ἀπέχοντας - 'دور بودند' - 'برخی دور بودند': 'τοὺς μὲν' - 'برخی'; 'ἀπέχοντας' - 'دور بودند'.
 - a. When an article is present, it is aligned together with the participle (N-N), unless the translation does not bear equivalent meaning. Example: πάντες δὲ οἱ καλούμενοι - 'کسانی که' - 'تمام کسانی که نامیده می شوند': 'πάντες' - 'تمام'; 'οἱ καλούμενοι' - 'کسانی که' - 'نامیده می شوند'.

7.2. Genitive absolute

The participle forming a genitive absolute is aligned with the corresponding translation in Persian, following the general rules of participles (1-1 or 1-N link type). The noun that agrees with the participle is aligned separately, with the corresponding translation in Persian. Example: ἐμεῦ ζῶντος - 'تا زنده ام' - 'ζῶντος' - 'من', 'ἐμεῦ' - 'تا من زنده ام'.

8. Prepositional phrases

Every component of a prepositional phrase is aligned separately with the corresponding Persian translation. Example: 'ἐν' - 'در', 'τῆ' - 'آن', 'νήσω' - 'جزیره'.

Sometimes a preposition will be translated to phrasal construction in Persian: such cases should be evaluated by the annotator to decide whether the translation is just partial or incorrect, and aligned accordingly.

9. Case uses

Inflected nouns (including substantivized adjectives, pronouns, etc.) are aligned with the corresponding Persian grammatical translation, provided that it bears equivalent meaning (1-N link). Any particle or adposition in Persian that conveys the meaning of the case (such as Ezafe or را) is aligned. Example: θεόν - 'ایزد را'.

Any modifier of the noun (attributes, determiners, etc.) does not obey this rule, since its inflection is considered to have originated from agreement with the noun.

There may be cases where the Persian preposition or particle is incorrect in the judgment of the annotator: in such cases, the annotator may align just the Ancient Greek word with the lexical translation and omit the preposition. Example: θεόν - ایزد - برای: Ø - 'برای', θεόν - 'ایزد'.

9.1. Vocatives

Nouns in the Vocative case in Ancient Greek are aligned to the corresponding translation in Persian. The exclamation (Ancient Greek 'ὦ' or 'ای' in Persian) is aligned to the corresponding word when present in both languages. When absent in one of the two, it is not aligned.

10. Pronouns and anaphoric structures

Pronouns are aligned as a 1-1 link with the corresponding word in Persian when they are equivalent in meaning.

Pronouns or other determiners (e.g. possessives, demonstratives, etc.) that replace a noun in one of the two languages but not in the other are not aligned. Example: 'ο' and 'Ἀγαμέμνων' are not aligned (even though it's the same person in the context).

11. Determiners (articles, etc.)

1. When determiners are present in both languages and are equivalent in meaning, they are aligned. Examples:
 - a. 'τις ἄνθρωπος' translated as 'مردی', is aligned as N-1, taking the attached *ς* as the equivalent of *تی*: 'τις ἄνθρωπος' - 'مردی'.
 - b. 'ὁ ἄνθρωπος' translated as 'این/آن مرد': 'ὁ' - 'این/آن', 'ἄνθρωπος' - 'مرد'.
 - c. Possessive adjectives are included among the options of acceptable translations. Example: τοὺς ἵππους, اسب‌هایشان را - 'τοὺς' - 'شان', 'ἵππους' - 'ها را'.
2. When a determiner is present in both languages, but they do not bear equivalent meaning, they are not aligned and only the noun is aligned. As a general rule, attached morphemes in Persian that do not reflect the Greek are ignored. Example: 'ὁ ἄνθρωπος' transl. 'مردی': 'ὁ' - Ø, 'ἄνθρωπος' - 'مردی'.
3. When the determiner is present in Persian in some form but not in Ancient Greek, it is not aligned. Example: 'ἄνθρωπος' - 'آن مرد': Ø - 'آن', 'ἄνθρωπος' - 'مرد'. As a general rule, attached morphemes in Persian that do not reflect the Greek are ignored; and therefore if the determiner in Persian is attached to the word, such as the indefinite *ς*, it is aligned. Example: 'ἄνθρωπος' - 'مردی'.
4. When the determiner is present in Ancient Greek but not in Persian: it is not aligned, unless absolutely necessary, i.e. in nouns that require the article in Ancient Greek. Examples: 'ὁ Κῦρος' - 'کورش', 'τῆ Εὐρώπῃ' - 'اروپا'. Incl. substantivizations of adjectives

and verbs in certain contexts. Examples: 'τὸν αἰσχρόν' - 'تنگ/امر] غير اخلاقی', 'τὸ μανθάνειν' - 'یادگیری'.

5. Phrasal translations are aligned to the group of determiner + noun, when they bear equivalent meaning. Example: 'τις ἄνθρωπος' - 'کسی'.

12. Pronominal uses of articles in Ancient Greek

Sometimes Ancient Greek uses articles with particles like δὲ as pronouns. Persian translations of this phenomenon differ quite significantly:

1. Pronominal equivalents: the whole expression in Ancient Greek is aligned with the corresponding Persian if they are equivalent in meaning. Example: 'Οἱ δὲ' - 'آنها', 'مردمان', etc. 'Οἱ δὲ' - 'کسانی که', etc.
2. Pronominal uses + prepositional phrases:
 - a. When translated literally, the pronominal expression is aligned with the corresponding Persian expression, and the prepositional phrase is aligned following the rules of prepositional phrases. Example: Οἱ δὲ ἐν τῇ νήσῳ - Those in the island: 'Οἱ δὲ' - 'آنان'; 'ἐν' - 'در'; 'τῇ' - ∅; 'νήσῳ' - 'جزیره'.
 - b. When translated with a close semantic equivalent: both groups are aligned, following the rules of idioms, with a N-N link. Example: 'Οἱ δὲ ἐν τῇ νήσῳ' - 'ساکنان جزیره'.
 - c. When translated with the addition of words not present in Ancient Greek: the additional words are not aligned, the rest is aligned according to the guidelines. Example: Οἱ δὲ ἐν τῇ νήσῳ - کسانی که در جزیره بودند: 'Οἱ δὲ' - 'کسانی که'; 'ἐν' - 'در'; 'τῇ' - ∅; 'νήσῳ' - 'جزیره', 'بودند' - ∅.

13. Adjectives and Adverbs

Adjectives and adverbs are aligned as individual lexical units, regardless of their function in the context (attributes, predicatives, nouns, etc.).

Comparatives and superlatives, which are usually single words in Ancient Greek, are aligned with the corresponding Persian translation, with a 1-1 link or, when necessary, a 1-N link.

Example: 'κάκιστος' - 'زشتترین'. If a comparative or superlative is translated to an adjective of a different degree or an adverb in Persian, it is aligned if the translation is correct in the judgment of the annotator.

14. Functional words and Particles

As a general principle, the functional words which are required for grammatical reasons are aligned when they have an equivalent counterpart in the other language. They are aligned with a 1-1 link if there is an equivalent Persian translation.

Exceptions and special cases:

1. ἄν (when not equivalent of ἔάν):
 - a. ἄν + Verbs: if the Persian translation of this group bears an equivalent meaning, then the group is aligned with a N-N or N-1 link to the Persian equivalent. If that is not the case, ἄν is not aligned. Example: 'ἄν ἔλθῃ' - 'بیايد'.
 - b. In fixed phrasal constructions, e.g. ὅπως ἄν: ἄν is aligned within the phrasal construction (N-1 or N-N link). Example: 'ὅπως ἄν' - 'همانطور كه / چنان كه'.
2. τε, μέν, δέ, γάρ, γε, δή et sim.: are aligned 1-1 to the corresponding Persian translation, if it is explicit, clearly identifiable, and isolated from other words.
 - a. τε καί group: when the translation is only one word, only καί is aligned. Example: 'τε καί': 'τε' - ∅; 'καί' - 'و'.
 - b. Combined uses (e.g. μέν + δέ, οὐδέ + οὐδέ, etc.): particles in combination can be aligned as a group to the corresponding Persian translation if they cannot be omitted without changing the meaning of the expression, and if the Persian translation bears an equivalent meaning to their function in combination. Example: 'μέν...δέ' - 'از طرفی... از طرف دیگر' or 'در حالی که', 'καί...καί' - 'هم...هم'.

Literature

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